

Impact of social media on consumer behavior

Asst.Prof. Shreya Singh

Mansi Nirwal

Professor of Galgotias University, Greater Noida UP 201310

Student of Galgotias university, Greater Noida UP 201310

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Abstract

Today, one of the most popular and extensively used channels of communication is social media. Social media is being used by people all over the world to communicate with one another. In recent years, people have turned to social media to share their stories. Experiences with a product, service, or platform are included as well. Thousands of individuals read these product reviews submitted by social media users every day, and they have become a source of consumer purchasing behaviour influence. After recognising the importance of this medium, businesses have begun to use it to promote their products and services. Today, social media is being used to sell products and services to a diverse audience. The goal of this study is to figure out what's going on in the world.

Introduction

Social media refers to a collection of software and web technologies that enable people to engage online, share material, and build a personalised network of friends, colleagues, or organisations. Every person uses their network in their own unique way, and there are no hard and fast rules regarding what is 'correct' for each site. The crucial term here, though, is social. Users use social media sites to communicate with friends, discuss ideas, and stay up to date on current events. They rarely log into their accounts with the intention of making a purchase. Even on career-oriented networks like LinkedIn, direct sales communications should be utilised sparingly and with caution. There are a variety of alternatives to merely putting 'buy me' messages for your book. You could think about it.

Write an article about your work and post a link to it in relevant groups and forums; remember to add a note about your book.

Join groups relevant to your work and keep an eye on other users' comments. Is someone asking a question you can answer? Then answer it and put in a link to your home page or blog or anywhere that your book can be found.

Something in the news relevant to your work? Make sure your friends and colleagues know it! In summary, social media works best when you join communities and participate in them. It won't generate much interest if you share a link to your book before anyone knows who you are. An announcement about your book, on the other hand, will be enthusiastically accepted if you have established a reputation as an active and productive contributor. If you want to learn more about social media, a fast search on Google or your favourite search engine will bring you a plethora of books, blogs, and websites. It is not difficult once you get started, though it does require a little effort and patience. Popular social media platforms that are used by companies to target their customers are:

1. Facebook

Facebook has 800 million users, making it a good place to promote your book to a potentially huge audience. You can sign up for an account at www.facebook.com

- Enables you to locate and join the networks of friends and colleagues.

Let's you share text, links, images and video to all your friends.

Encourages sharing of posts, so that friends of friends can see what you have posted. If they like, they also share it further on their own networks.

This multi-stage sharing across different social groups is one of the things that make Facebook so appealing as a place to mention your book.

There are a range of functions which you can explore, including

- o set up events and invite friends to attend.

- o set up a dedicated page (called a 'fan page') for you or your book where you can post news about the book or your other work.

- o set up your own special interest group, to discuss topics related to your research. Find out more about Facebook from Facebook's Getting Started guide.

2. LinkedIn

LinkedIn.com is a professional network, and profiles and posts are focused on work-related topics.

Contacts on LinkedIn are called Connections You can connect with others in your area, join specialist groups and forums and create a professional network with colleagues around the world.

When you create a LinkedIn account, you will be guided through the process for creating your professional profile, including experience, qualifications etc.

As well as posting messages (text, links, photos, video) you can make (and receive) professional endorsements.

It is an excellent place to mention your book as you are likely to be making contact with colleagues in an area similar to your own.

SlideShare was recently acquired by LinkedIn. It allows users to post slide presentations (e.g. using Microsoft PowerPoint) and share them with other users.

3. Twitter

You can share short tweets (under 240 characters), videos, photographs, links, polls, and more on Twitter. This platform makes it simple to communicate with your audience by referencing users in your posts, as well as like and retweeting tweets. Twitter is a terrific tool for fast spreading the word if you have interesting material and can speak it in an engaging way. Hashtags aid in the promotion of postings, and if a user with a large following retweet you, your work may go viral.

From the standpoint of a customer, social media is an essential tool for researching businesses and making purchasing decisions. According to Global WebIndex, 54% of social media users use the platform to research items, and 71% are more likely to buy goods and services after hearing about them on social media. Over 77 percent of individuals look at customer reviews before making a purchase. If a company has reviews, it creates credibility and trust rapidly (even if the evaluations are negative). Online reviews create the idea that your organisation is real and delivers a genuine product or service to potential customers. Customers from all around the world rely on these reviews to help them decide whether or not to buy a product. They also use these reviews to construct a brand image. Even if the reviews are negative, how the company responds to them can have a significant impact on the company's brand image. Through this research, I attempted to determine how much a social media advertisement can influence a consumer's purchasing decisions.

Literature Review

Social Media

Social media transports us back to a time when people lived in groups and clans and made decisions collectively as a result of their mutual influence. The term "social media" is a broad term that encompasses a variety of activities, practises, and platforms.

Etiquette in online groups of people that congregate to share information Using conversational media to share information, knowledge, and ideas (Web) based applications A website is becoming a requirement for most businesses. The social media material is considered part of a company's marketing mix. Viral marketing, which refers to the use of social media to spread information is developed. Is the tactic of encouraging website visitors to provide information published on the internet, to their friends, so that more people are informed through images and videos, for a product or event etc.

There are several sorts of social media

Blogs, microblogs (Twitter), social networks (Facebook, LinkedIn), media sharing (YouTube, Flickr), social news, and bookmarking are all examples of online communities (Digg, Reddit), Rating and review sites (Yelp), forums, and virtual worlds are all available (Second Life). Consumers gain from using them in a variety of ways, including saving time, having more information options, having more reliable information, having lower information costs, having better communication with companies, and having lower prices.

The Internet and social media were used by about half of the world's population, and this trend is rapidly increasing.

Consumer Behaviour

Individuals, groups, and organizations employ consumer behaviour to select, buy, and use products, services, ideas, and experiences to meet their needs and desires. It is a dynamic and intricate process. The way consumers behave and think is rapidly and continuously changing as a result of globalization and technological advancement. The consumer decision-making process is divided into five stages:

Stages 1- Need/problem recognition occurs when the customer notices a major discrepancy between his or her existing situation and a desired or ideal situation.

Stages 2- Information search

Stages 3- Alternative Stages

Stages 4- Buying

Stages 5- Post-purchase

Research Objective

I wanted to learn more about how social media influences the purchasing decisions of people of all ages through this study. The study will look into the numerous social media triggers and how people from various groups react to them. Another subject that has been covered in this paper is what factors contribute to customer dissatisfaction with social media marketing and campaigns?

By utilising the correct methods and using the proper social media platforms, any company, no matter how large or little, can tap into a wide audience and create a dialogue with not just their customers, but also potential customers and competitors.

Research Metrology

Research methodology refers to the procedures or strategies used to categorise, select, process, and interpret knowledge about a subject. A research paper's methodology section allows the reader to objectively analyse the study's overall validity and dependability.

Type of Research

The data for this study is primary in nature, and it was acquired by a self-administered questionnaire sent to people of various ages in India and the Middle East, mainly Kuwait. Questionnaires are a low-cost and rapid technique to assess a big group of people's behaviour, attitudes, preferences, views, and intentions. We may also quantify the level of a respondent's likelihood or unlikelihood to certain queries using various scales.

Research Design

The study is structured as a questionnaire, with questions aimed to provide the researcher with a comprehensive picture of how purchases perceive social media. Because the goal of the study is to develop ethnographic knowledge about the actions and shared beliefs of a specific group of people, a qualitative technique was chosen. It is easier to draw conclusions from the responses because this method is less controlled and more interpretative.

As a result, the questionnaire responses were used to acquire a better understanding of the impact of social media on customer purchasing behaviour.

Population and sampling collection

The questionnaire was filled out by people of all ages. Different age groups were chosen so that we could clearly grasp how different age groups perceived and felt about the questions being asked, as well as to introduce some variety in the data. The people who responded include students, employees, and housewives, among others...

The desirable characteristics that should always be taken into account while choosing a sample in order to maximise the yield Sampling considerations apply to the likelihood of successfully estimating population parameters.

As previously stated, the sample included responders of all ages.

- 18 - 25 : 66.3% population
- 26-40 : 15%
- 40 and above :24 %

Variable used

Dependent and independent variables are the two sorts of variables that can be employed in a study. It is required to establish a cause-and-effect relationship in order to make scientific discoveries. We employed independent factors such as age, gender, and other criteria such as social media platform preferences, irritation triggers, and so on for this study.

Scale Used

The following scales were used in the questionnaire:

Likert Scale: The Likert scale is the most widely used scale. Likert scale questions require respondents to select their level of agreement with a statement. Words like "highly agree," "agree," "don't know," and "disagree" could be used as response categories. **Nominal Scale:** A nominal scale is a measurement system for categorizing events or objects into discrete groupings. This scale does not employ numeric values or categories that are ranked by class; instead, each category is given a distinct identity. This scale has been used to answer questions about age, gender, and other factors.

Instruments used

This study was conducted using an EQuestionnaire since this method allows us to measure as well as monitor the opinions expressed by our respondents, allowing us to gain a better understanding of how each facet of social media influences consumer buying behaviour. The questionnaire was created and emailed directly to the respondents using "Google Forms," a survey software programme.

Aspects covered under the study:

The research is mostly focused on how social media influences consumer purchasing behaviour.

The following are the aspects that have been highlighted:

1. Product Review

2. Social Media advertisement

Are advertisements on social media effective? Do they have a good reputation among customers? Are these advertising actually seen by users? In the study, I aimed to answer these questions.

3. Brand Image

You make it easy for your clients to locate you and engage with you when you have a social media presence

Customer retention and loyalty are more likely to increase if you communicate with your customers on social media.

A social media presence is vital for a brand, according to 79 percent of respondents.

4. Annoyance Triggers

A variety of variables can cause people to get upset or annoyed by social media marketing. We have concentrated on three of these elements in our research:

- Length of content
- Over- Personalization
- Visual Appeal

Data analysis and interpretation

Figure 1

Which social media handle do you trust the most when it comes to product review?
10 responses

In Figure 1 YouTube is the most popular, whereas Pinterest is the least popular, according to a collective investigation. However, among those aged 40 and up, YouTube was the most popular. As a result, companies find Instagram and YouTube to be particularly appealing channels for marketing their products and services. Every month, 130 million Instagram users interact with commerce postings. Instagram allows you to share photos and videos. Without being overbearing, sell your business and products to your customers in a kind, genuine manner. When done correctly, online feedback can also serve to promote and improve the efficacy of your social media campaigns and media planning.

Figure 2

An advertisement of social media is likely to influence you to buy a product?
30 responses

In figure 2 It can be seen that the respondents are on the positive side of the spectrum when it comes to social media influencing them to buy a product; however, it's worth noting that only a small percentage of the respondents could confidently state that they are not influenced by social media advertisements.

According to a Deloitte analysis, consumers who use social media during their purchasing process are four times more likely to spend more than those who do not.

Figure 3-

Do you think having social media presence is essential for a brand ?

30 responses

In figure 3 We can see that 90 percent of respondents believe that a brand's social media presence is critical.

The fascinating element is that all of the respondents who believe a brand's social media presence is unimportant are above the age of 40. This is primarily due to the fact that the older generation does not place a high value on social media activity and visibility.

Figure 4-

Are you likely to change your decision to purchase a product if has gotten bad reviews on social media advertisement ?

30 responses

.In figure 4 It can be seen that if a product or brand receives negative feedback on social media, all of the respondents are more likely to reconsider their purchasing choice. This emphasises how critical it is for a firm to maintain a positive brand image and provide high-quality products. When a company receives a negative review, the worst thing they can do is disregard it. This has an impact not just on potential customers who read reviews, but also on recurring business. Another poor habit is taking an excessive amount of time to respond. Companies should have a plan in place to check their social media sites for feedback at least once a week

Figure 5-

Does extremely lengthy content into a social media advertisement frustrate you ?

30 responses

Figure 5 shows that 50% percent of respondents believe that reading content that is too long can frustrate them.

Companies should attempt to avoid using too many words or including unnecessary information in their advertisements. To avoid boring the viewers, social media advertisements should be succinct and to-the-point. The organisation should concentrate on the content it produces. In order to verify that the content shared on social media is error-free.

Figure 6-

Does extra personalization in an advertisement make you feel creeped out ?

30 responses

Over-personalization, according to 50 percent of respondents in Figure 6, can make customers feel uneasy and unsure about a business. They may believe that the company is utilising their personal information to boost sales and develop targeted ads. Companies should focus on providing compelling material for their social media pages rather than over-personalized content.

Figure 7-

Is visual clothing a key component of social media marketing?

28 responses

When it comes to social media advertisements, 77.8% of respondents believe that aesthetic appeal is vital. The respondents, particularly those over the age of 40, believe that graphics and videos entice people to watch commercials. Visual material is considerably more consumable and engaging than long-form blogs and posts.

Consumer interconnection via social media platforms including forums, reviews, and recommendations is anticipated to boost e-commerce trust. Consumers' social involvement on social networking sites (SNSs) helps or hinders their peers' faith in a supplier. Consumers' perceived trust is substantially influenced by the social relationships they form on social media (Pan & Chiou 2011). Social support is generated through interactions on various sites.

Conclusion

The study was driven by a personal curiosity in how consumer behaviour has altered in these technologically advanced times, particularly with social media. Every day, the amount of information available to us grows.

As a consequence, we are overwhelmingly exposed and acquired to various parts of information via the internet every day; as a result, we are overwhelmingly exposed and attained to diverse elements of information via the internet every day.

On the Internet, we have access to social media. Because of the accessibility and transparency that social media provides, it has becoming increasingly popular. Changes in how consumers place themselves in today's market, where it is unavoidable and expected, have resulted.

It is vital for businesses to develop a new marketing mindset. It's possible that the firm believes they're invincible.

Companies must make conscious efforts to stay up to date with the latest trends and come up with innovative and engaging content for their social media in today's Digital Age. Simply starting a Facebook page and posting pictures of the product is not enough to attract customers; they must make conscious efforts to stay up to date with the latest trends and come up with innovative and engaging content for their social media.

Users, regardless of their age or gender, use social media in some form or another while purchasing things. Either to read customer reviews, learn about current discounts and specials, or to learn more about the brand in general.

Companies should begin investing more in social media and concentrating on developing a strong social media presence. It is less expensive and reaches a larger audience in a shorter amount of time.

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